

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF TEACHERS' CHARACTERISTICS
ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-EFFICACY AND JOB
SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED
G.C.C.S.E PROGRAM**

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The Mediating Effect of Teachers' Characteristics on the Relationship Between Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction: Basis for a Proposed G.C.C.S.E Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of teachers' characteristics on the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction. This research employed a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing the descriptive correlation technique. The respondents of this study were the 117 high school teachers coming from the 4 different school of East and West Maitum District namely: Malalag National High School, Maguling National High School, James Alfred Strong Integrated School and Wali Integrated School. Based on the results of the study, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of preparedness, fairness, creativeness, compassionate, respect for learners, personal touch, sense of humor, forgiving, collaboration, and effectiveness in communication. Second, the level of teacher's self-efficacy was high in terms of student engagement, classroom management, and instruction strategies. Third, the level of job satisfaction was high in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities and community attachments/linkages. Lastly, there was a significant relationship between teacher's characteristics and self-efficacy, teacher's characteristics and job satisfaction, and self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Nevertheless, the result showed a partial mediating effect of teacher's characteristics on the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

Keywords: *educational management, teacher's characteristics, self-efficacy, job satisfaction, mediating effect*

Introduction

Job satisfaction is a crucial factor affecting teachers' well-being and performance worldwide. One of the leading global issues regarding teacher job satisfaction is the increasing workload and administrative responsibilities, which can lead to burnout and job dissatisfaction. In addition, inadequate compensation and limited opportunities for professional development can also contribute to a lack of job satisfaction. Moreover, the lack of autonomy and support from school management and the increasing pressure to meet standardized test scores can further demotivate and disengage teachers. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that involves improving working conditions, providing adequate compensation and professional development opportunities, promoting teacher autonomy and empowerment, and fostering a supportive school culture that values and recognizes the contributions of teachers (Kasalak & Dagyar, 2020).

Moreover, teachers' job satisfaction is crucial for individual teachers' well-being and the overall quality of education. When satisfied with their jobs, teachers are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and committed to their work, leading to better teaching quality and student outcomes. Less stress and burnout are experienced every day by teachers who are happy in their positions, which can eventually lead to better mental and physical health. High work satisfaction also plays a crucial role in attracting and retaining outstanding educators, which is necessary to preserve a stable and superior educational system. Thus, to enhance the quality of education and promote the well-being of teachers, educational institutions and legislators should place a high premium on guaranteeing work happiness among instructors (Ismayilova & Klassen, 2019).

In the Philippines, teachers' characteristics such as experience, education, training, personality, support from colleagues and administrators, and access to resources influence their self-efficacy beliefs and job satisfaction levels. Experienced and well-trained teachers tend to have higher self-efficacy and job satisfaction levels. Teachers' personality traits, such as extroversion, can also impact these levels. Support from colleagues and administrators is critical for higher levels of job satisfaction. Additionally, access to high-quality resources and materials can help teachers deliver effective instruction, increasing their self-efficacy and job satisfaction (Gonzales et al., 2020).

In Sarangani, the characteristics of teachers, including experience, education and training, personality traits, support from colleagues and administrators, and access to resources, can significantly impact their self-efficacy beliefs and job satisfaction levels. Experienced and well-trained teachers, extroverted personalities, and supportive work environments can increase self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Access to high-quality resources and materials can also lead to effective instruction and higher job satisfaction levels. To promote higher job satisfaction among teachers in Sarangani, professional development and support, recognition of their contributions, and mentoring programs for novice teachers are essential (Songcog & Guhao, 2020).

With the situation above of teachers' characteristics, job satisfaction, and self-efficacy, the researcher conducted this study to determine the mediating effect of teachers' characteristics on the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction in East and West Maitum District, Division of Sarangani, in the school year 2023-2024. An intervention program will be crafted based on the results of this study. This intervention program was tailored to address teachers' specific needs and characteristics in the East and West Maitum Districts.

This program hoped to improve the overall quality of education in the area by enhancing teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of teachers' characteristics on the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction as bases for an intervention program. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To determine the common teacher's characteristics in terms of:
 - 1.1. preparedness;
 - 1.2. fairness;
 - 1.3. creativeness;
 - 1.4. compassionate;
 - 1.5 respect for learners;
 - 1.6. personal touch;
 - 1.7 sense of humor;
 - 1.8 forgiving;
 - 1.9 collaboration; and
 - 1.10 effectiveness in communication.
2. To determine the level of teacher's self-efficacy in terms of:
 - 2.1. student engagement;
 - 2.2. classroom management; and
 - 2.3. instructional strategies.
3. To determine the level of job satisfaction of teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. security;
 - 3.2. work environment;
 - 3.3. job responsibilities; and
 - 3.4. community attachment/linkages.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. self-efficacy and job satisfaction;
 - 4.2. self-efficacy and teacher's characteristics; and
 - 4.3. teacher's characteristics and job satisfaction.
5. To determine the mediating effect of teacher's characteristics on the relationship between teacher's self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

Methodology

The section presents the method and procedure used in conducting the study. It includes the research design, locale, respondents and sampling techniques, research instrument, and data-gathering procedure employed in this study.

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, non- This research employed a quantitative design utilizing a descriptive correlation survey. Quantitative research design aims to gather numerical data and extrapolate it to other demographics. With this design, every detail is well thought out and planned before data collection. The researcher also has a well-defined research topic that is being answered objectively. Data includes things like numbers and statistics. According to Pérez Fuentes et al. (2020), the research may look at causal linkages, forecast future events, or generalize ideas more widely.

Moreover, quantitative design is a research approach that emphasizes collecting and analyzing numerical data to investigate and understand phenomena. It involves systematically measuring variables and statistical methods to analyze their relationships. Quantitative research aims to uncover patterns, trends, and associations that can be generalized to a larger population. In quantitative design, researchers typically formulate specific research questions or hypotheses and design studies that allow them to collect relevant data. They often use structured surveys, experiments, or observations to gather quantitative data, such as numerical measurements, ratings, or counts. The data collected are then analyzed using statistical techniques to test hypotheses, examine relationships between variables, and draw conclusions (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020).

Furthermore, deterministic philosophy originating from the post-positivist paradigm, or school of thought, is typically reflected in quantitative research designs. Post-positivists study causes and how various causes interact to shape results. The post-positivist perspective embraces the idea that reality can only be found imperfectly and in a probabilistic way. Usually, a deductive method is used, in which most ideas or concepts are reduced to variables, and their relationships are examined. The resulting knowledge is grounded in meticulous observation, measurement, and interpretation of the natural world as it is (Swart et al., 2019).

Furthermore, quantitative design is a research methodology that collects, analyzes, and interprets numerical data to gain insights into various phenomena. It employs a systematic and structured approach to study various topics, from social behaviors and market trends

to educational outcomes and health interventions. In quantitative research, investigators formulate specific research questions or hypotheses and design studies that allow them to collect data in a quantifiable manner. It often involves developing standardized surveys, questionnaires, or experimental protocols to gather data from a sample or population of interest. The collected data are typically numerical, including measurements, ratings, or counts (Pradana et al., 2020).

More specifically, this study has rejoiced in correlational design. First, teachers' characteristics, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction levels will be determined through scales. Then, the relationships among these variables will be explored. This study is correlational since it investigates the relationship between variables such as teachers' effectiveness according to their gender, location, years in service, and education. The survey questionnaire will be used to gather the primary data.

On the other hand, a correlational study is a type of research design that examines the relationships between two or more variables. With correlational research, a non-experimental research technique, two variables are measured, and the statistical relationship between them is understood and assessed independently of any other variable. Since correlational investigations are non-experimental, no variables are altered or under the experimenter's control (Seeram, 2019).

Similarly, a descriptive correlational survey is a research method that combines elements of descriptive research, correlational analysis, and survey design. It aims to describe and examine the relationships or associations between variables in a specific population or sample. This approach allows researchers to gather information about the variables of interest, measure their characteristics, and explore how they are related without manipulating any variables. In a descriptive correlational survey, researchers collect data using surveys or questionnaires that include predetermined questions or items related to the variables under investigation. The surveys are designed to capture information about the respondents' characteristics, attitudes, behaviors, or opinions on specific topics. The collected data are typically quantitative, involving numerical ratings or responses on Likert scales. The descriptive aspect of this method focuses on describing the variables of interest and their characteristics within the sample. Researchers often use measures of central tendency (such as mean, median, and mode) and variability (such as standard deviation) to summarize the data. These descriptive statistics provide a snapshot of the variables' distributions and help researchers understand the patterns and trends within the sample.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the 117 high school teachers from the four different schools of East and West Maitum District. There were 50 teachers from Malalag National High School, 42 teachers from Maguling National High School, ten teachers from James Alfred Strong Integrated School, and 15 teachers from Wali Integrated School. Slovin's formula was utilized to get the desired sample of the population. From 117 teacher-respondents, the final number of respondents was 91. Below is the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. *The Distribution of the Respondents*

School	Number of Teachers	
	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
Malalag National High School	50	38
Maguling National High School	42	33
James Alfred Strong Integrated School	10	8
Wali Integrated School	15	12
TOTAL	117	91

The researcher set the inclusion criteria for the respondents: male or female, regardless of religion and ethnicity, ages 30-50, who were currently teaching at Malalag National High School, Maguling National High School, James Alfred Strong Integrated School, or Wali Integrated School.

On the other hand, specific individuals were excluded from participation in this study, including those public secondary teachers ages 29 and above and 51. Additionally, respondents who were unable or unwilling to consent or cooperate in data collection were excluded from the study.

Nevertheless, respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Any respondent who chose to withdraw was assured that their decision would not have any negative consequences or impact on their relationship with the school or program. Furthermore, if any respondents displayed discomfort, distress, or emotional unease during the study, appropriate measures were taken to support and ensure their well-being.

Instruments

Three questionnaires were adapted from different Data from this study was gathered using five-point Likert-type scales. The scales of Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction, and Teachers' Characteristics were applied to obtain the research data. The data gathered in this study were then subjected to exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.

The first questionnaire was used to determine the teacher's level of characteristics. It was a researcher-made questionnaire based on an online website. It has ten indicators: prepared and positive, fair and creative, holding high expectations, compassionate and respectful students, displaying a personal touch, and having some sense of humor. Each indicator has 4 statements.

In evaluating the level of teacher's characteristics, the Likert scale below was used:

Scale	Range	Interpretation
1.0-1.7	Strongly Disagree	It means that the teacher's characteristics are not exhibited at all
1.8-2.5	Disagree	It means that the teacher's characteristics are exhibited at few times
2.6-3.3	Sometimes Agree	It means that the teacher's characteristics are exhibited occasionally
3.4-4.1	Agree	It means that the teacher's characteristics are exhibited most of the time
4.2-5.0	Strongly Agree	It means that the teacher's characteristics are exhibited at all times

The second questionnaire was used to determine the teacher's self-efficacy level. It was adapted and modified from the study of Seneviratne et al. (2019) entitled Teacher's Sense of Efficacy: A Challenge for Professional Development toward Teaching Science as Inquiry. It has 3 indicators. The first indicator is student engagement, which is composed of 6 statements. The second indicator is about classroom management, composed of 7 statements. The third indicator is about instructional strategies, comprising seven statements. In evaluating the level of teacher's self-efficacy, the Likert scale below was used:

Scale	Range	Interpretation
1.0-1.7	Very Low	It means that the level of self-efficacy is very low
1.8-2.5	Low	It means that the level of self-efficacy is low
2.6-3.3	Moderately High	It means that the level of self-efficacy is moderately high
3.4-4.1	High	It means that the level of self-efficacy is high
4.2-5.0	Very High	It means that the level of self-efficacy is very high

The third questionnaire was used to determine teachers' job satisfaction levels. It is adapted from the study of Romero & Bantigue (2017) entitled: 'Job Satisfaction Level of K12 Teachers Utilizing Multiple Statistical Tools. The instrument comprises four indicators: security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachment/linkages. Each indicator has ten statements. In evaluating the level of job satisfaction, the Likert scale below was used:

Scale	Range	Interpretation
1.0-1.7	Very Low	It means that the level of job satisfaction is very low
1.8-2.5	Low	It means that the level of job satisfaction is low
2.6-3.3	Moderately High	means that the level of job satisfaction is moderately high
3.4-4.1	High	It means that the level of job satisfaction is high
4.2-5.0	Very High	It means that the level of job satisfaction is very high

Data Collection

To pursue this study, the researcher collected data based on the book of Elsayed and Elsayed (2021) entitled "Fundamental of Research Methodology and Data Collection." The researcher made a questionnaire and asked expert validators to validate the instrument. Second, the research asked permission from the Ethics and Review Committee and Graduate School. Upon the approval of the request, the researcher asked permission to conduct the study from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent, Schools Division Office of the Division of Sarangani. The received copy was brought to the school heads where the study will be conducted. Fourth, the researcher prepared for reproduction according to the number of target respondents. After reproducing the questionnaire, the researcher personally explained the Informed Consent Form (ICF) and administered the questionnaire to the respondents. They will be given ample time to complete the questionnaires. Sixth, while retrieving questionnaires, the researcher checked if the respondents accomplished all the items. Finally, the completed questionnaires were summarized, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are crucial in this quantitative study. They encompass the study's approach, confidentiality, and anonymity. The research will strictly adhere to the ethical requirements set by the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee. It ensures proper treatment of the population and data, maintaining ethical standards throughout the study.

Voluntary Participation. Respondents were allowed to participate without any negative consequences or loss of benefits. Their rights were respected, and the study's purpose and benefits were communicated. Participation was voluntary, and respondents could withdraw if they felt uncomfortable.

Privacy and confidentiality. Respondents' privacy was respected in the study, adhering to the Data Privacy Act 2012. They can omit their names, and demographic information was withheld, ensuring confidentiality. Identity and survey responses were treated as private and kept secure.

Informed consent process. Respondents received detailed information, ensuring their understanding of the study's objectives, methods, and benefits. Their participation was voluntary, with written consent, and anonymity was maintained in the survey. Privacy was safeguarded, and withdrawal from the study was permitted.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. For the respondents to understand the study, the researcher explained its purpose for further inference and understanding of its essence. The researcher explained the purpose of the study and its importance in addition to the letter.

Risks. The study proceeded if the benefit-risk ratio was acceptable, prioritizing respondent welfare. Identity confidentiality ensured no harm to respondents, and their security was paramount. The researcher ensured that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially prepared. Their comfort and ease in answering the survey questionnaire were confirmed.

Benefits. This research has global implications for educational policies, teacher training, and professional development. It focused on improving teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction, positively impacting education quality and student outcomes. The study addressed a literature gap on the influence of teachers' characteristics on self-efficacy and job satisfaction. It highlighted the crucial role of teachers, benefiting stakeholders like parents, learners, and the community. The Department of Education can use the findings for policy formulation and enhancing school leadership. The study guides teachers and serves as a resource for future research.

Plagiarism. The study was checked for plagiarism using software like Grammarly to ensure originality. The researcher's integrity and understanding of plagiarism were crucial for a credible research paper.

Fabrication. The study maintained integrity by avoiding misinterpretation, fabricating data, or presenting inaccurate conclusions. The researcher integrated relevant theories and concepts to ensure the accuracy of the information presented.

Falsification. The study did not misrepresent the work to fit a model or theory, and there was no overclaiming or exaggeration. The data was manipulated or misleadingly presented, ensuring accuracy and integrity.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study was free from conflicts of interest and the disclosure of any such conflicts. The researcher did not control or influence the respondents, ensuring voluntary participation.

Deceit. The study did not mislead respondents about potential risks, and the rights of all respondents, particularly those with higher education, were vigorously protected. Appropriate and ethical standards were followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The researcher followed protocols by seeking approval from the RMMCERC, division superintendent, and school authorities. Public elementary school teachers involved in the study received orientation before administering the survey questionnaire.

Results

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the study's data are covered in this chapter.

3.1. The Common Teacher's Characteristics

Table 2 presents the data on the common teacher characteristics. The gathered data were treated using the mean.

Data analysis revealed that fairness was the most valued characteristic among teachers, with a mean score of 4.0. Fairness ensures equal opportunities and personalized support for all learners, recognizing diverse needs and adapting teaching methods accordingly. Treating students fairly fosters an inclusive environment that encourages growth and development for everyone. By treating all learners fairly in the educational setting, educators establish an inclusive environment that respects each student's unique abilities, encourages equal participation, and fosters growth and development for all individuals involved.

On the other hand, teacher's characteristic in terms of creativeness obtained the lowest mean score of 3.4 which means that teachers manifested creativeness was manifested often times. This score suggests that, while creativity is present, it may not be consistently applied within the classroom environment. The use of creativity in teaching is crucial for engaging students and enhancing learning experiences, yet the rating implies there is room for improvement. As educators strive to foster innovative thinking among their students, it is essential for them to also embody and exemplify creativity more regularly. Consequently, a focus on enhancing teachers' creative skills could lead to more dynamic and effective teaching methodologies, benefiting both educators and their students.

Table 2. The Common Teacher's Characteristics

Indicators	Mean n=91	Description
Preparedness	3.8	Agree
Fairness	4.0	Agree
Creativeness	3.4	Agree
Compassionate	3.9	Agree
Respect for Learners	3.9	Agree
Personal Touch	3.6	Agree
Sense of Humor	3.8	Agree
Forgiving	3.9	Agree
Collaboration	3.8	Agree
Effectiveness in Communication	3.7	Agree
Total	3.8	Agree

3.2. The Level of Teacher's Self-Efficacy

Table 3 presents the data on the level of teacher's self-efficacy in terms of student engagement, classroom management, and instruction

strategies. Mean was utilized to treat the gathered data.

Data revealed that teacher self-efficacy was high with an overall mean of 3.8. With regards with student engagement, the level of self-efficacy as high as shown in the mean of 3.7, indicating that teachers have various skills to help their students. They help students think critically, motivate those with low interest, boost student confidence, encourage a love of learning, foster creativity, and improve struggling students' understanding.

Moreover, teachers exhibit high self-efficacy regarding classroom management and instructional strategies. The mean score of 3.8 in classroom management indicates that teachers possess strong skills. They effectively communicate their expectations for student behavior, establish routines to maintain order, enforce classroom rules, handle disruptive students, implement management systems for group activities, and appropriately address defiant student behavior.

On the other hand, in terms of instructional strategies, the mean score of 3.8 reflects the teachers' confidence in their diverse instructional skills. They adeptly respond to challenging questions from students, assess student comprehension, formulate practical questions for student engagement, employ various assessment strategies, provide alternative explanations and examples when students are confused, utilize alternative teaching strategies as needed, and provide appropriate challenges for capable students

Table 3. *The Level of Teachers Self-Efficacy*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean n=91</i>	<i>Description</i>
Student Engagement	3.7	High
Classroom Management	3.8	High
Instructional Strategies	3.8	High
Total	3.8	High

3.3. *The Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

Table 4 presents the data on the level of job satisfaction in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachments/linkages. Mean was utilized to treat the data gathered.

Data revealed that job satisfaction was high as show in the overall mean of 3.8. Regarding security, the level of job satisfaction was shown in the mean of 3.7, indicating that teachers feel that the pay is sufficient, chances of promotion are high, and benefits are comparable to other organizations. Still, there needs to be more satisfaction with recognizing their efforts. The individual also feels that their job provides job security and opportunities for advancement. They feel they receive full credit for their work and can take pride in a well-done job. The individual also perceives that their pay is higher than that of similar companies and co-workers in school.

Moreover, the study revealed high job satisfaction among teachers regarding their work environment. The mean score of 3.8 indicates that teachers follow school policies, have a positive relationship with their heads, and experience a cooperative atmosphere with their colleagues. They also perceive good working conditions and enjoy friendly relationships with their co-workers. Additionally, teachers feel that their immediate head provides practical training, addresses employee concerns, and offers support during challenging situations.

Similarly, the study revealed high job satisfaction among teachers concerning their job responsibilities. The mean score of 3.9 indicates that teachers have diverse perceptions regarding their work, including opportunities to network with influential individuals, act ethically, advise colleagues, explore new ideas, utilize their skills, and innovate in their jobs without harming others. Teachers also appreciate the freedom to exercise their judgment and carry out their responsibilities without feeling dishonest towards anyone.

Teachers demonstrate high job satisfaction in terms of their community attachments and linkages. The mean score of 3.8 indicates that teachers feel a strong sense of belonging in the community and can contribute through small acts of service. They actively encourage stakeholder participation, considering themselves integral members of the community. Teachers engage in community outreach programs, address people's concerns, and foster strong connections between the school and the community. Furthermore, teachers appreciate the support provided by their heads in handling parental complaints. They see the school as welcoming to outsiders and recognize their job's significant social status.

Table 4. *The Level of Job Satisfaction of Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean n=91</i>	<i>Description</i>
Security (Salary, Benefits, Rewards Performance, Recognition, Promotion)	3.7	High
Work Environment (Policies, Organizational Structure, Physical, Emotional)	3.8	High
Job Responsibilities (Duties, Moral and Ethics)	3.9	High
Community Attachments/Linkages	3.8	High
Total	3.8	High

3.4. *Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction*

The significant correlation between work satisfaction and self-efficacy is displayed in Table 5. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to handle the collected data.

When self-efficacy and work satisfaction were measured, it was discovered that the data were measured at the 89 df alpha level, or 05. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. The null hypothesis was rejected because it exceeded the tabular value of 0.205. The teacher's self-efficacy highly impacted the degree of job satisfaction.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Job Satisfaction*

Variables	DF	rxy value n=91		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Self Efficacy vs. Job Satisfaction	89	0.79	0.205	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.5. Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Teachers' Characteristics

Table 6 shows the noteworthy correlation between teacher attributes and self-efficacy. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was utilized to manage the gathered data.

When the self-efficacy and instructor qualities were examined, it was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level 05 with a df of 89. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.81, as the table demonstrates. It was more important than the tabular value of 0.205. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. A notable degree of self-efficacy affected the teacher's traits.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Teachers' Characteristics*

Variables	DF	rxy value n=91		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Self Efficacy vs. Teachers Characteristics	89	0.81	0.205	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.6. Significant Relationship between Teachers' Characteristics and Job Satisfaction

Table 7 displays the noteworthy correlation between teachers' attributes and their level of job satisfaction. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was employed to handle the collected data.

When the traits and work satisfaction of the teachers were examined, it was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level. 05 with a pdf of 89. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.78, as the table demonstrates. It was more important than the tabular value of 0.205. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. The qualities of the teacher had a significant impact on how satisfied people were with their jobs.

Table 7. *Significant Relationship between Teachers Characteristics and Job Satisfaction*

Variables	DF	rxy value n=91		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Self Efficacy vs. Job Satisfaction	89	0.78	0.205	Reject Null Hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.7. On the Mediating Effect of Teacher's Characteristics

Table 8 presents the path analysis of the mediating effect of teachers' characteristics on the relationship between self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

The data revealed the direct effect of teacher's characteristics and self-efficacy, teacher's characteristics and job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. The routes with an unstandardized regression coefficient of.988, the standardized regression coefficient of.881, S.E., are teacher qualities and self-efficacy. at.029 and a probability level below 0.05. A low or tiny standard error indicates that the estimate is more accurate, and below the significance level of 0.05 suggests that these two variables have a meaningful association. The influence of efficiency, or effect size, is 96%, which is significant enough to reject the null hypothesis.

Additionally, the path b coefficient, which measures the self-efficacy and features of the instructor, has an S.E. of.120 for the standardized regression and.096 for the unstandardized regression. of.039 and a p-value of.020, both of which are below the 0.05 significant alpha threshold. As a result, there is a substantial correlation between self-efficacy and the traits of teachers. The effect size of teacher's characteristics and self-efficacy is 11%.

Finally, the path c coefficient displays the magnitude of the self-efficacy impact. The data result shows a p-value less than 0.05, a standardized regression coefficient of.752, an unstandardized regression coefficient of. 751, or 73% efficiency, and a computed standard error of. 051. It indicates a strong correlation between the variables. It lends mathematical credence to the notion that work happiness and self-efficacy are related.

Table 8. *Mediating Effect of Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)*

Path	Estimates		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
Teacher's Characteristics Self Efficacy	.988	.881	.029	27.122	***
Teacher's Characteristics Job Satisfaction	.096	.120	.039	2.401	.020
Self Efficacy Job Satisfaction	.751	.752	.051	14.542	***

Figure 3. Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship between Teacher's Efficacy and Teachers' Characteristics

Discussion

This section presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the data gathered.

The Common Teacher's Characteristics

The typical teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of preparedness, fairness, creativeness, compassion, respect for learners, personal touch, sense of humor, forgiveness, collaboration, and effectiveness in communication.

The common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of preparedness, indicating that teachers have a structured approach to teaching that involves a lesson plan, research, reviewing lessons before activities, preparing engaging materials such as slides or videos, and creating handouts on writing topics and activities. This assumption parallels the study of Liu et al. (2021), who claim that a teacher's level of readiness and capacity to conduct a lesson or teaching session successfully are referred to as their level of preparedness. A thorough understanding of the subject matter being taught is essential, as is lesson planning and organization, having clear goals and outcomes, foreseeing and addressing potential difficulties, and ensuring that all required supplies and resources are on hand. In addition to these technical elements, a teacher's preparation also involves their capacity to foster an environment that is supportive and stimulating for learning, build relationships with students, and modify their teaching methods to suit the various requirements of their pupils.

Further, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited mostly in fairness, indicating that teachers believe in equal opportunities and privileges for all learners, recognizing that fairness means giving everyone an equal chance to succeed. They acknowledge that not all learners learn at the same pace or in the same way and, therefore, provide explicit instruction and requirements to all learners. This assumption parallels the study of Soto and Rojas (2019), who claim that to be fair, a teacher should treat all students with respect, be consistent in their expectations and rules, provide equal opportunities for participation and learning, and avoid favoritism or discrimination based on factors such as race, gender, religion, or socio-economic status. Teachers should also be open-minded and willing to listen to different perspectives and ideas from their students and adjust their teaching approach to accommodate their student's diverse needs and learning styles.

Furthermore, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of creativeness, indicating that innovative teachers effectively use technology and instructional resources in the classroom. They are also actively involved in various school activities and continually seek ways to innovate and improve the learning experience. This assumption parallels the study of Ismayilova and Klassen (2019), who claim that creativity is an essential characteristic for teachers to possess because it enables them to engage

students in the learning process, make lessons more memorable, and foster a sense of excitement and curiosity in the classroom. Innovative educators can create lesson plans with various tools and instructional strategies, including group discussions, multimedia presentations, and hands-on activities.

Similarly, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited mostly in terms of compassion, indicating that teachers are compassionate, recognize when learners are struggling, and respond appropriately. They value each learner and teach with kindness and sincerity, allowing students to explore and make discoveries independently while providing guidance and support. This presumption is consistent with the research conducted by Yeves et al. (2019); compassion in education is defined as the capacity of an educator to empathize with their pupils, demonstrate care and concern for their welfare, and establish a safe and loving learning environment. Teachers must be compassionate to establish trusting connections with their pupils, foster a healthy learning environment, and give children a sense of security and worth.

The common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in respect for learners, indicating that teachers are considerate and respectful teachers who prioritize their learners' privacy and dignity. They avoid situations that may embarrass students and address grades or conduct privately. They are attentive to their students' feelings and open to hearing their concerns. This assumption parallels the study of Ahmed (2019), who claims that a teacher's respect for learners refers to their ability to value and honor each student's individuality, unique needs, and experiences. In addition to treating their children with respect, courteous educators foster a warm, inclusive classroom where each student feels important and accepted. Respectful educators work to foster a diverse classroom environment by acknowledging that every student has a distinct background, set of abilities, and life experiences. They take the time to get to know their students as unique individuals and modify their teaching style to suit their requirements and learning preferences.

Moreover, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited mostly in terms of personal touch, indicating that teachers value personal connections with their students. They are genuinely interested in getting to know their learners as individuals and ask about their interests outside of class. They encourage students to be engaged both in and out of the classroom. This assumption parallels the study of Riyanto et al. (2021); personal touches can take many forms, such as showing interest in students' lives outside of school, sharing personal stories and experiences, and creating opportunities for students to connect with the teacher. Personal touches can also involve incorporating student interests and hobbies into the curriculum or using humor and creativity to engage students in learning.

Likewise, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited mostly in terms of a sense of humor, indicating that teachers value personal connections with their students. They are genuinely interested in getting to know their learners as individuals and ask about their interests outside of class. They encourage students to be engaged both in and out of the classroom. This assumption parallels the study of Zahed-Babelan et al. (2019), who claim that a teacher's sense of humor refers to their ability to use humor appropriately and effectively in the classroom to engage students and enhance the learning experience. Pupils who are motivated, inquisitive, and enthusiastic about their studies are more likely to excel academically and develop a lifelong love of learning.

On the other hand, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of forgiving, indicating that a patient and understanding teacher forgives their students and starts each day with a clean slate. They refuse to give up on complex issues and strive to understand disruptive or antisocial behaviors. This assumption parallels the study by Hajiali et al. (2022), who claim that forgiving teachers are patient and supportive and are willing to work with their students to help them overcome obstacles and challenges. They provide constructive feedback and encouragement, rather than criticism or punishment, and focus on helping their students learn from their mistakes and improve their performance. Forgiving teachers also create a safe and supportive learning environment encouraging risk-taking and experimentation.

Hence, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited mostly regarding collaboration, indicating that teachers leverage their time with learners to establish deeper collaboration. They work together with a shared vision for the benefit of all learners and collaboratively design lessons to understand better how students learn and improve instruction. They also collaborate with learners to help them achieve shared goals and be more successful. This assumption parallels the study of Kelly et al. (2019), who claim that a teacher's collaboration refers to their ability to work effectively with colleagues, parents, and other professionals to support student learning and development. Collaborative teachers recognize that they are part of a larger educational community and that working together can improve student outcomes. Collaborative teachers share ideas, resources, and expertise with their colleagues and seek opportunities to work on joint projects and initiatives.

In addition, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time regarding effectiveness in communication, indicating that teachers employ practical communication skills to teach. They speak slowly and face their learners while teaching. They communicate through both speaking and writing and can articulate their ideas, discuss issues, and express their beliefs and values about teaching. This assumption parallels the study of Lazarides et al. (2021), who claim that effective communicators use various techniques to convey information to their audience, such as verbal communication, nonverbal cues, and visual aids. They also adapt their communication style to meet the needs of their audience, such as using simple language when working with younger students or adapting their tone and pace when communicating with students from diverse backgrounds.

The Level of Teacher's Self-Efficacy

The teacher's self-efficacy was high regarding student engagement, classroom management, and instruction strategies.

The level of teacher's self-efficacy was high in terms of student engagement, indicating that teachers have various skills to help their students. They help students think critically, motivate those with low interest, boost student confidence, encourage a love of learning, foster creativity, and improve struggling students' understanding. This assumption parallels the study of Kasalak and Dagyar (2020), who claim that student engagement refers to the level of involvement and interest students demonstrate in their learning experience. Students who are driven, inquisitive, and excited to study are more likely to succeed academically and cultivate a lifetime love of learning. Teachers can foster student engagement by creating a positive and supportive learning environment that promotes active participation, critical thinking, and collaboration.

Moreover, the teacher's self-efficacy level was high, indicating that teachers are skilled in classroom management. They make their expectations clear about student behavior, establish routines to maintain order, enforce classroom rules, handle disruptive students, establish management systems for group activities, and know how to respond to students who display defiance. This assumption parallels the study of Huang et al. (2019), who claim that effective classroom management also involves building positive relationships with students and creating a sense of community and belonging. Teachers can achieve this by taking the time to get to know their students, providing opportunities for collaboration and teamwork, and recognizing and celebrating the accomplishments of their students.

Additionally, teachers' self-efficacy regarding instructional strategies indicated that teachers possess various instructional skills. They respond to difficult questions from students, assess student comprehension, create good questions, use multiple assessment strategies, provide alternative explanations/examples when students are confused, implement alternative teaching strategies, and provide appropriate challenges for every capable student in their classroom. This assumption parallels the study of Burić and Moe (2020), who claim that instructional strategies refer to the techniques and methods teachers use to facilitate student learning and engagement. Effective instructional strategies are based on learning theory and are designed to promote student understanding, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. These strategies include direct instruction, inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, cooperative learning, differentiated instruction, and technology-enhanced learning.

The Level of Teacher's Job Satisfaction

The level of job satisfaction was high in terms of security, work environment, job responsibilities, and community attachments/linkages.

The level of job satisfaction was high in terms of security, indicating that teachers feel that the pay is sufficient, chances of promotion are high, and benefits are comparable to other organizations. Still, there needs to be more satisfaction with recognizing their efforts. The individual also feels that their job provides job security and opportunities for advancement. They feel they receive full credit for their work and can take pride in a well-done job. The individual also perceives that their pay is higher than that of similar companies and co-workers in school. This presumption is consistent with a study by Steijn and Van der Voet (2019), which contends that teachers who feel valued and supported by their employers have more confidence in their ability to plan for the future and are more likely to experience job satisfaction. Furthermore, districts and schools prioritizing teacher security are more likely to draw in and keep top-notch instructors, enhancing student performance and fostering a more pleasant school climate overall.

Further, the level of job satisfaction was high in terms of the work environment, indicating that teachers follow the school's policies and practices, have a good understanding of their head, and have a spirit of cooperation among co-workers. They also feel that the working conditions are good, and they can easily befriend their co-workers. The individual perceives that their immediate head trains their subordinates well, handles employee complaints, and provides help in difficult situations. This assumption parallels the study of Perera and John (2020), who claim that the job responsibilities of teachers involve educating and guiding students in their academic, social, and emotional development. Teachers design lesson plans, develop curriculum, and create assessments to evaluate student learning.

Furthermore, the level of job satisfaction was high in terms of job responsibilities, indicating that teachers possess different perceptions related to work, including opportunities to network with influential people, the ability to act according to one's conscience, giving advice to co-workers, trying new things, utilizing one's abilities, developing new and better ways of doing the job, without harming co-workers, having the freedom to use one's judgment, and doing the job without feeling like cheating anyone. This assumption parallels the study of McLean et al. (2019), who claim that the job responsibilities of teachers involve educating and guiding students in their academic, social, and emotional development. Teachers design lesson plans, develop curriculum, and create assessments to evaluate student learning.

Similarly, the level of job satisfaction was high in terms of community attachment/linkages, indicating that teachers feel that they have a definite place in the community, can provide small services to others, encourage stakeholder participation, be a big part of the community, participate in community outreach programs, help address people's concerns, strengthen linkages with the school and the community, and that their head takes care of complaints from parents. The individual also perceives that the school community is pleasant towards external stakeholders and that their job carries a social position within the community. This assumption parallels the study of Paaís and Pattiruhu (2020), who claim that community attachment or linkages of teachers refers to the extent to which teachers are connected to and engaged with the communities in which they teach. Teachers with solid community attachments are more likely to understand their students' needs and cultural backgrounds and to work collaboratively with families and community organizations

to support student learning.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the following conclusions were made: First, the common teacher's characteristics were exhibited most of the time in terms of preparedness, fairness, creativeness, compassion, respect for learners, personal touch, sense of humor, forgiving, collaboration, and effectiveness in communication. Second, the teacher's self-efficacy was high regarding student engagement, classroom management, and instruction strategies. Third, job satisfaction was high regarding security, work environment, responsibilities, and community attachments/linkages. Lastly, there was a significant relationship between teacher's characteristics and self-efficacy, teacher's characteristics and job satisfaction, and self-efficacy and job satisfaction.

The following recommendations were formulated based on the results: The Department of Education may provide ongoing and relevant professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and self-efficacy. Offer training in classroom management, technology integration, and culturally responsive teaching practices. Ensure that professional development is aligned with the needs and goals of teachers and the school. School administrators may create a culture of supportive leadership that values and recognizes the contributions of teachers.

Moreover, to strengthen the relationship between the variables, school administrators may implement a system of regular feedback and evaluation to help teachers understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Constructive feedback and recognition of their accomplishments can enhance teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction. The department should establish clear evaluation criteria and provide timely and meaningful feedback to support teachers' professional growth. Further, to enhance teachers' creativity, schools can foster a culture of experimentation and collaboration, providing professional development workshops, encouraging cross-disciplinary cooperation, and promoting technology to support innovative teaching practices.

To support instructors in enhancing their instructional strategies and boosting their self-efficacy, school administrators may offer frequent coaching and feedback. Ensure the leadership is attentive to the needs of the instructors and dedicated to fostering a supportive work environment. In addition, teachers may undergo various seminar workshops related to self-satisfaction to strengthen their sense of pride and lessen their burnout. Lastly, this study may be used as the basis for future research.

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